

Synthetic tests: unconstrained multiple level set inversions with errors in the starting model and noise in the data

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1 Introduction

This document reports tests of the level set inversion of Giraud et al. (2021) extending their testing using:

1. Starting models that are significantly different from the reference model used to generate the data.
2. A high level of random noise contaminating the data.

Building upon the synthetic case presented in Giraud et al. (2021), I investigate four scenarios where the starting model deviates increasingly from the true model. Following this, I test the inversion of a dataset contaminated with unrealistically high noise. In example 5, the data is contaminated with zero-mean normally distributed random noise characterized by a standard deviation of 5 mGal.

2 Synthetic model and survey setup

The presentation of the synthetic survey setup below is a repeat of Giraud et al. (2021).

“The synthetic model I used in this work (Figure 1) is built from a 2D cross-section reproducing features inspired by the staircase scenario of Li and Oldenburg (1996). To increase the complexity of the model, I assigned two distinct density contrasts to the largest dipping structure (left-hand side of the horizontal axis, representing, for instance, the overriding plate of a convergent margin) and added three disks of differing density contrasts to the initial model (right-hand side of the horizontal axis, representing, for instance, mid- to lower-crustal magmatic complexes). Including the background, this model requires the utilization of $N = 6$ signed-distance functions, each attached to the closed surface defining geological structures with densities equal to 2670, 2770, 2845, 2870, 2900, and 2950 Kg/m^3 , respectively.

Figure 1. True model used to generate synthetic geophysical data. The white lines show the outline of the geological bodies modeled here. Labels in the figure indicate the index of the level-set function modeling the respective bodies they are in.

The model is discretized in $n_x \times n_y \times n_z = 270 \times 1 \times 60$ cells of size $d_x \times d_y \times d_z = 2533 \times 30339.6 \times 2533 \text{ m}^3$. The data inverted for in this synthetic study (Figure 2a) is generated on a profile comprised of $n_d = 270$ data points located at surface level along the x -direction. [...] To evaluate the capability of our inversion algorithm to recover the true model accurately and to fit the geophysical data, we monitor the root-mean-square (RMS) error for both data and model. We calculate these indicators as follows:

$$\begin{cases} ERR_d = \sqrt{\frac{1}{D} \sum_i^D (d_i^{obs} - d_i^{calc})^2}, \\ ERR_m = \sqrt{\frac{1}{M} \sum_i^M (m_i^{true} - m_i^{inv})^2}, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where D is the number of data, M is the number of model-cells; \mathbf{m}^{true} and \mathbf{m}^{inv} are the true and inverted models, respectively; and \mathbf{d}^{obs} and \mathbf{d}^{calc} are the observed and calculated data. [...] In what follows, we test our inversion algorithm using an objective ERR_d value [...] which matches the noise level simulated.”

3 Examples

3.1 Example 1 – small bias and error in starting model

The starting model m^{start} I use here overestimates the volume of the dipping bodies (left-hand side) and misplaces the centre of masse of, and interface between, the leftmost bodies (Figure 2b). The associated forward response d^{start} (Figure 2a) produce $ERR_d = 17 mGal$ and the model presents $ERR_m = 61 kg/m^3$.

Inversion converged after 11 iterations. The geophysical data fit of the inverted model can be evaluated visually using Figure 2a. The inverted model is shown in Figure 2c, while the evolution inversion of ERR_d and ERR_m is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Example 1: test using a starting model that underestimates the size of units 3, 4 and Synthetic data overlaid with starting 5 and inverted data (a), starting model (b) and model recovered from inversion (c). The white lines materialize the outline of the geological bodies modelled here.

Qualitatively, the visual comparison of the inverted and true model in Figure 2 shows that the geometries of all geological bodies present good agreement with the true model. Notably, the dipping body in the leftmost part of the model is well recovered and much improved compared to the starting model. Even if inversion improves the imaging of the central dipping object, it is comparatively less well recovered than the other objects, with the inverted volume appearing more rectangular than the convex parallelogram used in the true model. This may be an effect of the non-uniqueness inherent to geophysical inversion.

From Figure 2a, it is important to note that geophysical data fit is consistent along the horizontal axis and that all parts of the model are honouring the data equally well. Overall, the decrease of the data fit during inversion shows that the inverted model is stable, as are other indicators (Figure 3), and that inversion converges relatively quickly.

Figure 3. Inversion metrics for example 1: data RMS (ERR_d , left), model RMS (ERR_m , right).

3.2 Example 2 – moderate bias and error in starting model

Similarly to the previous example, the starting model \mathbf{m}^{start} I simulate here overestimates the volume of the dipping bodies (left-hand side) and misplaces the centre of masse of, and interface between, the leftmost bodies (Figure 4b). Bodies 1 and 3 were shifted to the left and downwards. The forward response \mathbf{d}^{start} (Figure 4a) and the model \mathbf{m}^{start} present $ERR_d = 17.5 \text{ mGal}$ and $ERR_m = 62.5 \text{ kg/m}^3$, respectively.

Inversion converges after 11 iterations. Similarly to the previous example, the geophysical data fit of the inverted model can be evaluated visually (Figure 4a). The inverted model is shown in Figure 4c, while the evolution inversion quality indicators ERR_d and ERR_m is shown in Figure 5. The evolution of data misfit is similar to example 1, while ERR_m increases slightly before plateauing after iteration 5, which can be an effect of the non-uniqueness of gravity inversion.

Figure 4. Example 2: synthetic data overlaid with starting and inverted data (a), starting model (b) and model recovered from inversion (c). The white lines materialize the outline of the geological bodies modelled here.

Comparably to the previous example, the right section of body 1 (in between 120 km and 150 horizontal position) presents the features of a rectangle, while the sphere 5 and the outline of the leftmost dipping bodies are well recovered. Body number 3 (leftmost sphere) is less well recovered than in the previous example, however. A potential explanation is that the algorithm decreased data misfit by enlarging both body 3 and 4 simultaneously. Consequently, body 3 being farther away in this example, the influence of body 4 became stronger. The shape of body 3 is distorted as a result of gravity data's lack of vertical resolution.

Figure 5. Inversion metrics: data RMS (ERR_d , left), model RMS (ERR_m , right).

From the results obtained for example 1 and 2 I can conclude that, in cases where prior information is not providing models that differ vastly from the cause bodies, level-set inversion is capable of recovering geometries that are close to the true model and can be used for hypothesis testing, interpretation and further modelling. The next step of the evaluation of the technique proposed here pertains to testing extreme case scenarios, which I show below using example 3 and 4.

3.3 Example 3 – large bias and error in starting model

The starting model m^{start} I simulate here largely overestimates the volume of all bodies, misplaces their centre of masse and their interfaces (Figure 6b). The starting data is, at every measurement location, higher than the synthetic field data. This translates into the corresponding forward response d^{start} (Figure 6a) and model m^{start} presenting $ERR_d = 31 mGal$ and $ERR_m = 71 kg/m^3$, respectively, which are noticeably higher than in the previous two examples.

Figure 6. Example 3: synthetic data overlaid with starting and inverted data (a), starting model (b) and model recovered from inversion (c). The white lines materialize the outline of the geological bodies modelled here.

Visually, inversion results shown in Figure 6 indicate a model fit similar to examples 1 and 2 to the exception of sphere 5, which is too shallow, and of the contact between sphere 3 and 4 which is not recovered. Inversion quality indicators in Figure 7 show convergence of the inversion similar to example 1 with inversion stopping after 11 iterations.

Figure 7. Inversion metrics for example 3: data RMS (ERR_d , left), model RMS (ERR_m , right).

3.4 Example 4 – extreme bias and error in starting model

The starting model m_{start} I simulate here largely overestimates the volume of all bodies, misplaces their centre of masse and their interfaces (Figure 8b). The starting data is, at every measurement location, lower than the synthetic field data. This translates into the corresponding forward response d^{start} (Figure 8a) and model m^{start} presenting $ERR_d = 32 mGal$ and $ERR_m = 75 kg/m^3$, respectively.

Figure 8. Example 4: synthetic data overlayed with starting and inverted data (a), starting model (b) and model recovered from inversion (c). The white lines materialize the outline of the geological bodies modelled here.

Overall, the main features of the true model are recovered, to the exception that the two dipping bodies in the leftmost part of the model are not in contact anymore.

Figure 9. Inversion metrics for example 4: data RMS (ERR_d , left), model RMS (ERR_m , right).

3.5 Example 5 – test using noisy geophysical data

In this example, I test the case with a synthetic dataset contaminated by noise characterised by a normal distribution centred on 0 with a standard deviation of 5 mGal. This dataset is shown in Figure 10a. The starting model is shown in Figure 10b and the inverted model is shown in Figure 10c. We note that the starting model is the same as the synthetic model without bias used in Giraud et al. (2021), i.e., assuming an accurate estimation of the rock units' densities and the presence of an erroneous small anomaly in around 190 km horizontal position not present in the true model. The inversion metrics are shown in Figure 11 and show that the inversion converges to a stable solution in 11 iterations.

Figure 10. Example 5: synthetic data overlaid with starting and inverted data (a), starting model (b) and model recovered from inversion (c). The white lines materialize the outline of the geological bodies modelled here.

Figure 11. Inversion metrics for example 5: data RMS (ERR_d , left), model RMS (ERR_m , right).

Overall, the observations made above demonstrate the potential of the proposed inverse modelling scheme to refine the geometry of geological bodies. The different scenarii tested here improve the data fit and reduce the model misfit significantly.

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5 References

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